

Effect of transition metal cations on the production of citric acid using mixed cultures of *Aspergillus niger* and *Candida guilliermondii*

Ar. Angumeenal^a, P. Kamalakannan^b, H. J. Prabhu^c and D. Venkappayya^a

^aDepartment of Chemistry, ^cDepartment of Chemical Engineering, Regional Engineering College, Tiruchirappalli-620 015, India

E-mail : dvenka@rect.ernet.in

^bDepartment of Chemical Engineering, Lake-Head University, Ontario, Canada

Manuscript received 26 December 2002, revised 11 April 2003, accepted 2 June 2003

Mixed culture technique was applied to citric acid production. Selected transition metal ions, namely, cadmium, lead, chromium and molybdenum were added in calculated quantities during fermentation and their effect on the metabolic path followed by the microbes was studied. Cadmium was dragged inside the cell across the membrane to balance the proton motive force and was found to increase considerably the citric acid production. Lead was found to suppress the transport pump by strengthening cell wall cross links, whereas chromium activated the pump thereby inducing production. The possible reasons are discussed.

Reports reveal the use of single cultures for batch fermentation of citric acid¹⁻⁹. Hitherto no attempts are reported on the study of effect of cadmium, chromium, lead and molybdenum as nutritional supplements on the production of citric acid by *Aspergillus niger* and also on the use of cocultures for the production of citric acid. In view of the above, an attempt was made to explore the effect of the above mentioned transition metal ions on the various physiological and biochemical changes taking place during the course of citric acid production by the molds namely *Aspergillus niger* and *Candida guilliermondii*.

A fermentation medium comprising of glucose (14%), KNO₃ (0.8%), K₂HPO₄ (0.125%), MgSO₄.5H₂O (0.02%) and ZnSO₄.7H₂O (0.02%) was sterilized (by autoclaving at 15 lbs for 15 min), cooled and brought to a pH of 3-4. Various metal ions namely cadmium (20, 40, 60, 80, 100 ppm), chromium (5, 10, 20, 30, 50 ppm), lead (20, 40, 60, 80, 100 ppm) and molybdenum (5, 10, 15, 20, 25 ppm) were included into the media before inoculation of the fermentation media with the microbes namely *Aspergillus niger* and *Candida guilliermondii*, procured from N.C.L., Pune with the following specification : "NRRL 322 - Species for Citric Acid Production CMI 31276; NCTC 594; WB 322", and NCIM 3126 respectively.

From the third day of inoculation, the culture broth was filtered and analysed for residual metal ions, anions, total titrable acidity (volume of 0.1 N NaOH consumed by 1 mL of the filtrate), citric¹⁰, succinic and malic acids and extra-cellular soluble proteins¹¹. The biomass was analysed for

lipid¹², amylase¹³, and protein contents.

Results and discussion

From the fermentation using mixed cultures of *A. niger* and *C. guilliermondii* it was found that the amount of citric acid produced was higher than with single culture alone⁹. The control medium with single culture (*A. niger*) was found to produce a total titrable acidity of 5 mL/mL and 25 mg/mL of citric acid whereas the production was higher by 15% with cocultures. The metabolic changes of *A. niger* were found to remain unaffected.

Effect of metal ions on cocultures and citric acid production :

Effect of cadmium : The amount of total, citric, succinic and malic acids determined in the filtrate accompanied by the change in the growth of *A. niger* are given in Table 1. A maximum amount of 109 mg/mL of citric acid with a total titrable acidity of 12.2 mL/mL was produced by cocultures with 60 ppm cadmium in the medium. The growth of *A. niger* in the presence of *C. guilliermondii* was not affected which was discerned from the higher change in biomass weight.

In all the enzyme catalysed reactions the first step is the formation of enzyme substrate complex followed by the product formation. In the case of citric acid production the substrates are acetyl coenzyme-A (acetyl CoA linked to a terminal SH group) and oxaloacetate. In the presence of cadmium which is a soft acid and which has greater tendency to bind with sulphur, easy bond formation can occur between

Table 1. Effect of metal ions on the metabolism of *Aspergillus niger*

Metal ion (ppm)	TTA mL/mL	CA mg/mL	Biomass g/100 mL
Cadmium			
20	12.0	102	3.254
40	12.6	101	3.488
60	12.2	109	3.460
80	8.7	69	3.090
100	8.7	71	2.650
Lead			
40	4.2	31.0	2.092
60	6.0	22.0	2.060
80	5.6	25.0	1.950
100	6.5	27.0	1.866
Chromium			
5	9.2	20.8	2.318
10	13.5	22.8	2.754
20	13.2	30.0	2.522
30	13.8	31.7	2.554
50	4.3	13.2	1.164
Molybdenum			
5	4.7	21.6	2.904
10	3.5	26.3	2.156
15	4.0	30.2	1.982
20	3.7	25.2	1.504
25	3.7	28.1	1.678

TTA = Total titrable acidity CA = citric acid

sulphydryl groups of acetyl CoA and cadmium. Due to this greater ease of metal substrate complex formation, higher amounts of citric acid are produced. The mechanism would have been the same in both the molds, which caused a remarkable increase in the citric acid production with cadmium as a supplement in the fermentation medium. According to chemiosmotic hypothesis, as electrons flow through the electron transport chain at certain steps, H^+ ions are pushed out from the membrane. This builds up a proton gradient leading to the accumulation of negative charges. To balance this proton motive force cadmium is dragged inside across the membrane.

Effect of lead The maximum amount of citric acid detected in the filtrate of cocultures with lead was found to be 31.0 mg/mL at 40 ppm of lead. The amount of citric acid produced was almost the same (32.7 mg/mL) as with *A. niger* alone. A considerable increase in the intracellular and extracellular proteins were observed compared to the mold metabolism with other metals. The increase in the protein metabolism is due to the supply of nitrogen from *Candida*

as a feed for *A. niger*. As the filtrate has metabolites due to the combined metabolism of *A. niger* and *C. guilliermondii*, it is richer in proteins when compared to single culture. The amounts of acids and proteins produced in the filtrate with cocultures are shown in Table 1.

It was observed that in coculture studies, lead was toxic to the carbohydrate metabolism of *Candida* and its contribution towards the synthesis of citric acid via the TCA cycle was almost nil. It was noticed that with lead in the fermentation medium, both in single culture and coculture studies, the normal cell processes were not affected. This was confirmed from the amounts of acids and proteins produced which were comparatively higher than with single culture i.e., with *A. niger* alone. Likely, membrane permeability is affected because protein chains provide a variety of weak bonds which form a tight packing and therefore affect the transport of substances in and out of the cell. It is reasonable to assume that lead is responsible for strengthening these cross links and thereby suppress the transport pump.

Effect of chromium The quantities of total, citric and succinic acids produced by mixed cultures viz., *A. niger* and *C. guilliermondii* estimated after fermentation are given in Table 1. The total titrable acidity was found to be 13 to 14 mL in the fermentation medium with cocultures which is double the amount as that with single culture alone. However, the maximum amount of citric acid produced was considerably more with mixed cultures with chromium in the medium. It was also noticed that the molds (cocultures) were found to produce more succinic acid than citric acid.

In the presence of chromium, the electron transport chain must have activated the proton pump releasing an increased H^+ into the fermentation medium as a result of which high total titrable acidity was observed because microbe can use metals as electron donors in energy metabolism.

Aconitase is the enzyme present in molds with less activity. It is involved in the conversion of citrate to isocitrate, which is later converted to α -oxoglutarate (via the TCA cycle or to glyoxylate cycle). The activity of aconitase should be less for the accumulation of citrate in the medium. On increase in the activity of this enzyme the dominating product will not be citric acid and hence an increase in succinic acid production was observed.

The active centre of the afore-mentioned enzyme contains Fe^{2+} and a thiol group. Normally in the native form, this enzyme is less active in molds. In the presence of chromium at higher concentrations, due to the higher nuclear charge it would have gone into the active site by competitive binding and therefore the enzyme exhibits a slight change

in activity. As a result, citric acid is isomerised to aconitic acid with greater ease of bond formation the dominating product identified was succinic acid with 50 ppm chromium in the medium with cocultures. This was not found to occur with single culture (*A. niger*) where the dominating product identified was only citric acid. It can thus be concluded that the mechanism proposed above (abnormal aconitase activity) would be operative in the case of *Candida*.

The intracellular proteins identified in *A. niger* in coculture studies were higher with low chromium in the medium. Further, increase in the concentration of chromium in the medium did not affect the production of intracellular proteins. The same trend was observed with extracellular proteins in the culture filtrate of cocultures. This could be due to the chelation of chromium with nitrogen whereby nitrogen (of amino acids) became unavailable for peptide synthesis and hence a decrease in proteins was observed with increase in concentration of chromium in the medium. Another probable reason could be due to the formation of peptidoglycans. Here again, the biomass of *A. niger* was not affected by the presence of *C. guilliermondii*.

Effect of molybdenum : Molybdenum in the form of ammonium molybdate was added to the fermentation medium. Batches were run with 5, 10, 15, 20 and 25 ppm of molybdenum. A maximum of 30.2 mg/mL of citric acid was identified in the culture filtrate, which was fermented with cocultures and had a concentration of 5 ppm in it. Trace amounts of succinic acid were detected in the medium. The amounts of intracellular and extracellular proteins were found to be the same as in *A. niger* at all concentrations of molybdenum in coculture studies. The total titrable acidity produced was less with cocultures than with single culture but the amount of citric acid produced was more with cocultures. It was found that 16.9 mg/mL of citric acid was produced by fermentation with *A. niger* alone which increased to 30.2 mg/mL on using *A. niger* and *C. guilliermondii* for fermentation. Hence it can be assumed that the metabolism of *C. guilliermondii* was found to be augmented by the presence of molybdenum. The amylase activity in *A. niger* was not affected by the presence of *C. guilliermondii* (30 to 35 U/mL/min). The amount of extracellular soluble proteins was found to be 0.2 to 0.3 g/100 mL with cocultures. Molds produce nitrate reductase enzyme, which is inactive. The activity of nitrate reductase enzyme is restored by the acid hydrolysis products of other enzymes synthesized by the microbe. The reduction in total titrable acidity may be ascribed to the neutralization by the amino nitrogen and due to the increased nitrate reductase activity of molybdenum clusters in the enzyme. The possible

reason for more citric acid with cocultures may be due to the chitin-glucan complex present on the cell wall along with the lipid bilayer. The lower activity of chitin synthase leads to the synthesis of very weak polysaccharide cell wall. The formation of a weak cell wall leads to an effective transport of the metabolized product in *Candida*. So higher quantities of citric acid is produced.

Experimental

Estimation of metal ions :

The metal ions in the culture media were analysed before and after fermentation using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer GBC 902 in an air/acetylene flame.

Estimation of citric, succinic and malic acids :

All the acids were determined using HPLC, Shimadzu LC 10 AT equipped with uv-vis/thermal detector. The aliquot was analysed in the isocratic elution mode using 0.2 M H₃PO₄ (mobile phase) in the ODS column. Citric acid produced was also cross-checked with Marrier Boulet's method, where an aliquot of the filtrate was mixed with pyridine and acetic anhydride. The yellow colour developed was measured at 420 nm.

Estimation of proteins :

The amino acids present in the proteins developed a blue colour with Folin ciocalteau's reagent and alkaline cupric tartarate, which was measured at 620 nm to estimate intracellular and extracellular proteins. To estimate intracellular proteins an aliquot of the filtrate after fermentation was used and for extracellular proteins microbial tissue extract was used.

Estimation of amylase :

The reducing sugar produced by the action of amylases reacts with dinitrosalicylic acid and reduces it to a red coloured amino salicylic acid whose colour intensity was measured at 560 nm to get the amylase activity.

Estimation of lipids :

The biomass on extraction with CHCl₃/CH₃OH mixture was dissolved in H₂SO₄ and treated with vanillin reagent (0.2% in H₃PO₄) to get a red colour which was measured at 510 nm.

Conclusion :

The coculture studies with *A. niger* and *C. guilliermondii* revealed that the production of citric acid can be considerably increased (109 mg/mL) with cadmium as a stimulant. *C. guilliermondii* was found to be more active in producing citric acid in the presence of cadmium. Presence of lead in the medium had no effect on the metabolism of *Candida*.

With chromium at a concentration of 50 ppm, succinic acid was produced in greater amounts compared to citric acid. This was not observed with single culture studies, where *A. niger* alone was used for fermentation. Hence it is suggested that the above effect is due to the change in enzyme activity of *C. guilliermondii*. Molybdenum was also found to exhibit a stimulatory effect in *C. guilliermondii*. It was thus observed that *C. guilliermondii* was found to induce and increase the rate of citric acid production with *A. niger*. There was no risk of any mutation while using cocultures.

References

1. Roukas and Triantafyllou, *Appl. Biochem. Biotechnol.*, 1998, **74**, 43.
2. Sarangbin, Somyak, Watana Pakasin and Yuwadee, *Carbohydr. Polym.*, 1999, **38**, 219.
3. Kirimura, Kchitaro, Watanabe, Taisei, Sunagawa Tadaihiro, Usami and Shoji, *Biotechnol. Biochem.*, 1999, **63**, 228.
4. Ewaryst Elimer, *Food Technol. Biotechnol.*, 1998, **36**, 189.
5. T. Roukas, *Enzyme Microb. Technol.*, 1999, **24**, 54.
6. Leangon, Sirichom, Maddox, Ian S. Brooks and D. John, *World J. Microbiol. Biotechnol.*, 1999, **15**, 493.
7. M. Papagianni, M. Matthey and B. Kristiansen, *Enzyme. Microb. Technol.*, 1999, **25**, 710.
8. Yuguozheng, Wang Zhao and Xialong Chen, *Process Biochem.*, 1999, **35**, 237.
9. Ar. Angumeenal, P. Kamalakannan, D. Venkappayya and H. J. Prabhu, *Indian J. Chem. Technol.*, 2002, **9**, 153.
10. M. Marrier and Boulet, *J. Dairy Sci.*, 1958, **41**, 1683.
11. O. H. Lowry, N. J. Rosebrough, A. L. Farr and R. J. Randall, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1951, **193**, 265.
12. J. Folch, Lee and Sloane-Stanley, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1957, **226**, 497.
13. Peterfield, "Methods in Enzymology", eds. S. Colowick and N. O. Kaplan, Academic Press, New York, 1955.